

Farmers' participatory evaluation of saline-tolerant rice varieties

L. Ponnusamy and N. Thenmathi, Central Institute of Brackishwater Aquaculture, Indian Council of Agricultural Research, 75 Santhome High Road, Chennai 600028, Tamil Nadu, India

Promising salt-tolerant lines should undergo on-farm evaluation to validate recommendations for their wider adoption (Jauhar Ali et al 1999). Low rice yield caused by soil salinity and water stress was assessed by farmers through a participatory rural appraisal (PRA) under a World Bank-funded National Technology Project (NATP) called "Institution Village Linkage Program for Technology Assessment and Refinement in the Coastal Agro-Ecosystem of Tiruvallur District of Tamil Nadu." We conducted the present investigation with farmers to assess the performance of rice varieties (Trichy 1 and Trichy 2) grown by farmers and to evaluate their salinity tolerance.

PRA tools were used for problem identification, field trials, monitoring and evaluation, and sending farmers' feedback to the research and extension system. The field study was carried out in Kattur, Tiruvallur, Tamil Nadu, during *samba* (Aug 2001 to Jan 2002). The farmers grow White Ponni, ADT43, and BPT5204 and are dependent on rainfed tank irrigation. These varieties are not salt-tolerant. Weather is moderately warm, with rainy periods between October and December. Soil of the village is moderately drained clay loam with a pH of 7.4. The soil has low available N, me-

dium P, and high K content.

A matrix ranking was used to compare the three rice varieties. Ranking was carried out by a group of farmers and triangulated (cross-checked) with other group extension functionaries.

Farmers preferred White Ponni because of its stable yield, profitability, taste, and slender grain (Table 1). Though BPT5204 gave better yield and profit, it was more susceptible to pests and diseases. However, these varieties did not tolerate saline conditions. At the same time, whenever there is not enough rainfall during the northeast monsoon, water stress reported during the end of crop growth results in low rice yield. Near the sea coast, where soil salinity is high, the yield of White Ponni was low.

Farmers thus felt the need for saline-tolerant, short-duration rice varieties to mitigate the problems of water stress and salinity.

Seeds of saline-tolerant varieties Trichy 1 and Trichy 2 were obtained from the Agricultural College and Research Institute, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University. On-farm trials were conducted in 10 farmers' fields (area was 0.4 ha each). White Ponni was taken as the control.

The grain yield of Trichy 1 increased by 8% and that of Trichy 2 by 4.8% compared with that of the control.

Table 1. Matrix ranking of existing rice varieties by farmers in the study village.^a

Characteristic	White Ponni	BPT5204	ADT43
Yield	5	3	2
Yield stability	5	3	2
Risk in cultivation	1	5	3
Profitability	5	5	3
Seed availability	5	5	5
Susceptibility to pests and diseases	1	5	4
Tolerance for weed infestation	5	2	4
Tolerance for water stress	4	1	3
Labor use	5	2	2
Compatibility with weather	4	1	2
Taste	5	3	4
Digestibility	4	5	4
Grain size	Slender	Short, bold	Bold
Straw yield	5	3	4
Parched rice-making quality	5	3	4
Duration (d)	155–160	140	115–120
Lodging/nonlodging type	Lodging	Nonlodging	Nonlodging

^aOn a scale of 1–5, where 1 = least/minimum and 5 = maximum/higher/more/best. Yield scores are based on visual assessment by farmers.

Table 2. Evaluation of saline-tolerant varieties.

Item	Farmer's variety (White Ponni)	Trichy 1	Trichy 2
Panicles m ⁻² (no.)	268	255	250
Filled grains panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	98.2	89.7	95.4
1,000-grain weight (g)	15.2	24.3	22.4
Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	3.75	4.05	3.93
Straw yield (t ha ⁻¹)	5.17	5.54	5.23
Per day productivity (kg)	23.23	26.13	32.75
Returns (US\$ ha ⁻¹) ^a			
Cost of cultivation	228.33	224.58	200.77
Gross returns	578.31	524.48	507.75
Net returns	349.98	299.89	306.98
Benefit-cost ratio	2.53	2.33	2.52

^aUS\$1 = 48 rupees.

Similarly, the respective straw yields (7.15% and 1.06%) and productivity (12.48% and 40.9%) of Trichy 1 and Trichy 2 were significantly higher than those of the control (White Ponni). But the net returns from growing White Ponni were higher because of its fine grain, whereas the Trichy varieties fetched a low market price because of their coarse grain.

Further, one-way analysis of variance was carried out with these three rice varieties to study the differences in mean yield performance. The

results showed that yields of these three varieties differed significantly from each other at the 2% level of significance. Duncan's multiple range test was conducted to achieve multiple comparisons. The analysis revealed that the varieties are different. Trichy 1 (4.5 0.05) had better yield than Trichy 2 (3.39 vs 0.98) and White Ponni (3.75 vs 0.44). The farmers were also convinced of the satisfactory performance of Trichy 1 and Trichy 2. We need well-designed on-farm trials to evaluate the performance of

Trichy 1 and Trichy 2 under saline and water-deficit conditions.

Reference

Jauhar Ali A, Somasundaram E, Nanamohammed SE, Rajagopalan R, Rajukkannu K, Subramanian M. 1999. Rice in coastal saline soils of Tamil Nadu. In: Vistas of rice research. Aduthurai, Tamil Nadu: Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute.

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Deepwater agroecosystem characterization and system diagnosis of farmers' problems in Bihar, India

U.P. Singh, Department of Agronomy, Institute of Agricultural Sciences, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi 221005, Uttar Pradesh, India E-mail: u_psingh@sify.com/upratap@banaras.ernet.in

The deepwater rice (DWR) environment is so variable and complex with regard to hydrology that it cannot be duplicated at the research center, where technology is generated. Consequently, the technology does not perform well in farmers' fields. In certain areas, on-station technology may be adopted by farmers, but it fails completely in other areas. There is therefore a need to classify the different agroecosystems for on-station and on-farm research. The DWR area in Bihar constitutes about 1.1 million ha, with productivity averaging 1.0 t ha⁻¹. This area falls under one of the most complex, diverse, fragile, and risk-prone environments.

An agroecosystem analysis of flood-prone DWR environments of north Bihar showed that rice is the only crop that thrives well in deepwater conditions. Rice is followed by late wheat or boro rice. Mixed cropping is practiced in limited locations in some areas. The usual practice in deepwater *chours* is to broadcast rice with mungbean, sesame, sorghum, maize, or *Capsularis* jute. However, in the low-rainfall season, the cropping pattern is DWR, followed by winter-season cereals, pulses, and oilseeds, depending on available soil moisture status. Normally, in very deepwater areas, water remains year-round and transplanting is

practiced. In deepwater areas, cropping patterns vary according to rainfall or flood patterns. Rice-fish farming is also practiced in deepwater areas. After the harvesting of rice (Dec-Jan), local fish such as Mangur, Singhi, Bhakur, Rohu, and Katla are also harvested. No supplemental food was given to the fish.

A system diagnosis of farmers' problems was done through participatory rural appraisal and problem ranking/prioritization. The exercise showed lower and unstable production potential of the DWR ecosystem. The key problem pointed out by the farmers was poor DWR yield. The biophysical causes identified were irregular hydrol-